

CITIZENSHIP AND STATELESSNESS: AN ASSESSMENT OF THE ROHINGYA PEOPLE'S STRUGGLE IN SOUTHEAST ASIA

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Abstract

Humanitarian catastrophe the Rohingya people of Myanmar are exposed to is unprecedented. They have been stripped of citizenship and all attendant benefits; driven out of their ancestral home across the border to Bangladesh; and left at the mercy of benefactors. Their pathetic situation prompted this research with a view to understanding the immediate and remote issues involved in the crisis. Descriptive and analytical methods were adopted in the study. It was found out that the Rohingya crisis is rooted in their support of British Imperialism against largely Buddhists Burmese support of Imperial Japan during the First and Second World Wars. Since independence in 1948, the Buddhist majority have decided to punish the minority Muslim Rohingya culminating in stripping them of citizenship in 1982. Attempts to resist unbearable conditions such as poor access to education, healthcare, employment, seizure of properties, etc., have triggered state crackdown on ethnic Rohingya, forcing hundreds of thousands to flee to neighbouring countries. The study therefore, recommends that the Citizenship Law of 1982 should be repealed immediately; and the Government is urged to call the military out of the Rohingya areas immediately, otherwise, the UN should place crippling sanctions on Myanmar state officials and the top brass of the military.

1.1 Introduction

Citizenship is a precious possession. It is even more precious if it is conferred by birth. Citizenship conveys several rights and privileges. It opens the doors to education, employment, property ownership, political office, etc. These privileges though extended to immigrants, have often unwritten limitations.

Every child born ought to belong to parents. The child's home should be the parent's home as well as his birthplace. In this connection, Article 15 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights says "everyone has the right to nationality and no one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his nationality or denied the right to change his

nationality” (UNCHR, 1978:7). Signatories to the United Nations Charter are mandated to domesticate this law as a part of their national laws. If that is done conscientiously, no man, woman or child would be stateless.

Unfortunately, many today are without citizenship or have been deprived of one. The case in focus in this study is the Rohingya people of the Southeast Asia. They are found in the Myanmar western state of Rakhine. The Rohingya have had a troubled history dating some centuries. They were effectively stripped of citizenship of Myanmar by the 1982 Citizenship Decree. Since then, the Rohingya have been object of attack by opposing individuals, groups and state apparatus. These attacks have increased in scope and intensity, forcing hundreds of thousands of ethnic Rohingyas to seek refuge in neighbouring Bangladesh or across the Indian Ocean to Indonesia, Malaysia, and Thailand. Trapped in statelessness, the Rohingya refugee situation is the most pressing humanitarian crisis today. It has attracted the attention of the international community led by the United Nations Organisation, international donor and relief organisations as well as kind spirited individuals.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

Republic of the Union of Myanmar (former Burma) has a long history of conflicts - conflicts among the ethnic nationalities of Myanmar as well as conflicts with colonial forces of Japan and Britain. Since independence from Britain on January 4th, 1948, Myanmar Rohingya group have had to deal with organised attacks allegedly linked to their support of Britain against Japan during the Second World War (Eleanor, 2017). Various regimes in Myanmar have restricted the Rohingya freedoms culminating in the 1982 Citizenship Law which effectively stripped the Rohingya of access to full citizenship and right to self-identity.

As noted by the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO) factsheet, the Rohingya are subjected to many restrictions in day-to-day life: banned from travelling without authorisation, prohibited from working outside their villages, and cannot marry without permission. There are also restrictions on family planning, education, religious choice and entertainment (ECHO, 2018).

The Rakhine state that houses the Rohingya is the least developed with more than 78% of households living below the poverty line (World Bank, 2017). Widespread poverty, weak infrastructure, and a lack of employment opportunities exacerbate the cleavage between Buddhists majority and Muslim Rohingya minority. Massive anti-Rohingya sentiments began in 1978 and culminated in the military junta operation to

purge Burma of “illegal inhabitants which saw about 250,000 flee to Bangladesh” (Human Rights Watch, 2015). This tension is deepened by religious violence which broke out in 2012, when a group of Rohingya men were accused of raping and killing a Buddhist woman. Frustration led to a series of attacks and killing of security forces by perceived Rohingya militia along Myanmar-Bangladesh border in October 2016, prompting an inflow of military and police personnel for manhunt of those responsible. Again, on August 25th, 2017, a group under the banner name of Arakan Rohingya Salvation Army (ARSA) attacked several police stations and outposts killing some officers. The result has been an on-going crackdown by Tatmadaw (Myanmarese Army) on local Rohingya population. UNCHR (2018) reports that atrocities, rape, destruction of properties that included burning of several Rohingya villages by the Myanmar army forced an estimated 800,000 Rohingya population to cross the border to seek shelter in Bangladesh. The situation is referred to as the biggest humanitarian crisis of modern history by both the Red Cross and UNHRC. The displaced Rohingya are in dire need of basic supplies such as safe drinking water, food, sanitary materials, clothes, medicine and shelter. Meanwhile, Bangladesh authorities say the country has been stretched to the limit. It is therefore, imperative to undertake this study to understand the root cause of this crisis, especially as it relates to the controversial citizenship law of 1982.

1.3 Research Questions

- In what ways does the 1982 Citizenship Law of Myanmar influence the Rohingya crisis?
- How does ethno-religious differences factor in on the Rohingya crisis?
- To what extent has that composition of Myanmar contributed to the Rohingya crisis?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

While the broad objective of this research is to examine the perceived influence of the 1982 citizenship law of Myanmar on the statelessness and humanitarian emergency of the Rohingya people, other sub-objectives include:

- To review efforts of stakeholders on the Rohingya crisis;
- To proffer practical recommendations to address the crisis.

1.5 Research Methodology

This is the blueprint of action as it concerns the extant research. According to Eboh (2009, p. 8), “research design is a deliberate strategic approach used in conducting a scientific enquiry”. It answers the ‘what’, ‘where’, ‘when’, ‘how’, and “by what means” questions of a research.

This research is qualitative in nature, hence, descriptive and analytical methods were adopted. This approach helped the researcher to draw available data systematically and analysed same. In descriptive research, the researcher is involved in ex-post study, that is, the researcher reports only what manifests without any control over the variables of study (Eboh, 2009). In other words, the researcher observes and then describes what was observed. Since scientific observation is careful and deliberate, scientific description is bound to be more accurate and precise than casual descriptions.

1.6 Literature Review

a) Conceptual Review

The definition of displaced individuals as a result of persecution overlaps considerably with that of stateless persons, who are described by the UN (1954) as individuals not considered as a national by any state. For such persons, accessing basic rights such as healthcare, employment, education and freedom of movement is often difficult. Lack, denial or loss of nationality underlie the exclusion of affected individuals from membership in the community, to the point of instigating discrimination and oppression in certain cases. There are approximately 10 million stateless people and approximately 1.5 million people who are refugees in addition to being stateless (Ullah, 2011). Groups such as the Nubians of Kenya, the Bedouin of Kuwait, the Kurds in Syria, the Yao and Hmong hills tribes of Thailand, the Roma in Europe, and the Rohingya of Myanmar are effectively stateless.

A citizen on the other hand is a lawful member of a community. He has unfettered rights and privileges conferred by law; and by virtue of citizenship, an individual can aspire to the highest office in the land.

b) The Rohingya

The Rohingya in Myanmar are one of the most persecuted minorities in the world. The majority are not considered to be citizens by the Myanmar Government, hence, live in a condition of statelessness. The Rohingya are a Muslim ethnic minority situated primarily in Myanmar's western Rakhine state and are estimated to be about one (1) million people. They have been fleeing Myanmar in large numbers often to nearby developing countries, particularly Bangladesh, Malaysia and Thailand—to avoid conflict and persecution (Albert, 2017). Correspondingly, the refugee crisis in Bangladesh has reached critical levels, with the number of unregistered Rohingya refugees estimated to range between 700,000 to 800,000 people (UNHCR, 2018).

The plight of the Rohingya dates back centuries. Rohingya's history can be described in three epochs: pre-colonial, colonial and postcolonial.

In pre-colonial times, the independent kingdom of Arakan (currently known as the Rakhine State), was populated by Muslim Arabic sailors from 788 to 810 AD, and afterwards by Bengalis from the fifteenth to the seventeenth centuries (Ahmad, 2014). During the pre-colonial times, the Rohingya and Arakanese (the remainder of the population in Arakan) lived in harmony.

In the colonial epoch, this changed after colonization by the British following the first Anglo-Burmese war in 1825. The rift deepened during the Second World War, when the Rohingya declared their loyalty to the British, while the Arakanese sided with the Japanese (Ullah, 2011). During the Japanese occupation of Burma (including Arakan), the Rohingya population was targeted jointly by both the communalist (Buddhist) Rakhine and the Burma Independence Army, killing 100,000 Rohingya and exiling 50,000 towards East Bengal (HRW, 2000).

After Burma received independence in 1948, the anti-Rohingya campaign persisted, marked by discrimination and denial of their citizenship rights. Around this period (between 1940 and 1947), Buddhist fundamentalist extremism was on the rise. Eventually, in 1978, the amassed anti-Rohingya sentiment culminated in the military junta operation to purge Burma of illegal inhabitants. This led to the flight of 250,000 Rohingya to Bangladesh. Faced by pressure from the international community, a repatriation agreement was struck with Bangladesh the following year, resulting in the majority of Rohingya being returned to Burma. However, just three years later, Burma passed the 1982 Citizenship Law that denied citizenship to Rohingya, decreeing an estimated 800,000 Rohingya in North Rakhine stateless. Rohingya are not recognized as a national race by the Burmese government even if there is evidence that they were born in the country. Instead, they are identified as "Bengali" illegal immigrants.

During the military junta rule in 1988, the State Law and Order Restoration Council (SLORC) established a number of new military cantonments in the Rakhine State, focusing on the north where Muslims were situated. Lands were forcefully taken from the Muslim inhabitants without compensation, thereby rendering the Rohingya both 'homeless' and 'stateless'. Branded as illegal residents, they experienced basic human rights violations including denial of access to education, healthcare, employment, freedom of movement, religion and even limited rights to get married

or have children (Abul, Mijanur, Sumaira, Charulata, Sushmita, Shahnaz, Shahana, Tafzila, John and Jimmy, 2017).

The ongoing anti-Rohingya campaign and extreme circumstances has resulted in a persistent exodus of the Rohingya to safer neighbouring countries, where they reside as stateless refugees. Bangladesh has been the preferred destination for the majority of asylum-seeking Rohingya because of the initial recognition of their humanitarian needs along with close proximity and matching religion. Many have taken the risk of crossing the ocean to Malaysia, Thailand and Indonesia instead of nearby India, China or Laos. From 1991–1992, there was another influx of about 250,000 Rohingya refugees to Bangladesh owing to military crackdown in Myanmar due to the failed democratic election in 1990. Although the majority of refugees were repatriated to Northern Myanmar during the following decade, many of these sought their way back to Bangladesh. After 1992, Rohingya entering Bangladesh were not officially recognized as refugees by the Government of Bangladesh (GOB). However, large numbers of Rohingya arrived once again in Bangladesh during late 2016, following a massacre in Myanmar where hundreds of Rohingya were murdered, faced with sexual violence and thousands of houses were burned down.

The on-going crisis started in August 25th, 2017 when a group under the banner name of Arakan Rohingya Salvation Army (ARSA) attacked several police stations and outposts killing some officers. Now the army is conducting massive and systematic rape, burning of villages, beatings, maiming, detaining, and killing of ethnic Rohingya. UNHCR (2018) reports that atrocities, rape, destruction of properties that include burning of several Rohingya villages by the Myanmar army has forced estimated 800,000 Rohingya population to

Figure 1.1 Internally Displaced Camp Burned by the Army in Rakhine State
Source: Council on Foreign Relations, 2018

cross the border and seek shelter in Bangladesh. The situation on ground is desperate and urgent and is referred to as the biggest humanitarian crisis of modern history by both the Red Cross and UNHCR. The displaced Rohingya are in dire need of basic supplies and consumables such as safe drinking water, food, sanitary materials, clothes, medicine, shelter and a sense of safety.

1.7 Theoretical Underpinning

Society is governed by the consent of its members, implicitly or explicitly expressed. Consent theorists hold that the laws of the society, whether about property, crime or punishment represent the way of life of the society and its ultimate will, and operate by the consent of the whole population. The people would, therefore, obey the laws spontaneously because they were the very source of the laws and had voluntarily adopted them. This work adopts Consent Theory of Political Obligation as its framework of analysis. According to John Locke quoted in Eminue (2001, p. 182), “consent entails acceptance and readiness to obey; an approval of individual or group to excise political authority”. It is often said that consent is “morally transformative,” even magical - it transforms what otherwise would be illegal conduct into conduct that is entirely legal.

In both the history of political theory and popular consciousness, the idea that political obligations rest on consent has played a dominant role. It is a common feature of popular discourse and important public documents. For instance, according to the *Declaration of Independence*, governments derive their just powers from the consent of the governed. The idea that people must agree to their obligations to government is supported by the great weight liberal political theory places on values of liberty and autonomy. As Harry Beran puts this, rights to self-determination should extend to political self-determination. People should be under political authority only if they put themselves under it (Beran, 1987).

In his essay, "Of the Original Contract", David Hume notes the great appeal of consent as a basis for political obligations: "where it has place", he writes "It is surely the best and most sacred of any." But Hume also notes that it has very seldom had a place in any degree (Hume [1748] 1985, p. 474; D. Hume, 2012).

By political obligation, theorists generally mean a moral requirement to obey the law of one's country. Traditionally, this has been viewed as a requirement to obey the law *because it is the law*, which is generally taken to mean that political obligations are "content-independent." In other words, reasons to obey stem from the authority of the legislator as opposed to the content of particular laws (see Hart 1958; 1982). This view has a long provenance, dating back at least to the time of Thomas Hobbes. According to Hobbes, "Command is where a man saith, *Doe this* or *Doe not this*, without expecting other reason than the will of him that says it." (*Leviathan*, Chap. 25; [1651] 1991, p. 176). Since moral requirements to obey laws follow from the means through which they are made rather than their content, legislators are able to establish obligations to obey all the laws that they make. A great strength of consent theory is its comprehensiveness, its ability to account for all political obligations. And since consent places obligation on both the governed and governor, bridge of agreement means termination of consent.

In this connection, it has been postulated by consent theorists that if the state fails to provide protection, social welfare and happiness for its citizens, the people could dissolve it (Eminue, 2001). That's why John Locke, one of the famous consent theorists, argues that Government could be dissolved (through a rebellion by the people) if the Government fails to guarantee the citizen's right to life, liberty and property.

One can see very clearly how this theory fits the present study. The Rohingya people have been stripped of their inalienable rights. The 1982 citizenship law made by a military junta has no place in common sense and international law. The people have been declared “Bangals” or illegal residents. They have been driven out of their residents, denied access to education, employment, medication and farms. Meanwhile, the primary purpose of government is to guarantee the security and welfare of citizens. As noted by Locke, the Social Contract Theory was entered by citizens who consented to be ruled by the government who gave guaranteed rights over life, property and liberty (Navari, 1991). Since the Myanmar Government has deliberately exposed the Rohingya people to hate, it becomes incumbent on the people to revolt against the state. There is no justification for declaring a people who have lived peacefully for centuries illegal residents. Therefore, any form of resistance by the Rohingya to defend itself should be seen as self-protection.

Consent theories, like most theories, have criticisms. For instance, Hart (1982) argues that consent is a powerful basis for political obligations, but only on a theoretical level. It suffers from the significant defect of inapplicability to actual political conditions. Attempts to make it apply have been unsuccessful, either failing to account for the obligations of most citizens or distorting what is ordinarily meant by consent in attempting to do so.

1.8 Stakeholders in the Rohingya Crisis

Key actors in the Rohingya situation include:

- Government of Myanmar
- Myanmar security forces
- Rakhine State
- Myanmar other ethnic nationalities
- Leadership of Buddhist religion
- The Rohingya people
- Bangladeshi government
- Southeast Asian nations
- Humanitarian agencies
- The international community

Source: Sage Journals. Sage pub.com

A look at this list reveals that the stakeholders are many and diverse. None should be mistaken or undermined in finding a way to lasting peace. However, the three most

critical actors are the government, security forces and the people of Myanmar. To begin, the people give life to government and government lives by the will of the people. So, the people and government are one. The security apparatus is a creation of the state and lives by the will of government. Yes, the security forces can impose its will on both the people and government in view of its manipulation of weapons. But a people's resolve can neutralise any weapon of war.

It is true that the military looms large in Myanmar and that has contributed to the near to nothing effort of the State Counsellor, Aung Sang Suu Kyi's Government. The government is basically winking at the onslaught by the army on the Rohingya, but what is being done to address the migration crisis?

Myanmar's first civilian government led by Aung San Suu Kyi's opposition National League for Democracy (NLD) party won in landslide elections in November 2015. While the cabinet ministers include a mix of political and ethnic representatives, critics say the NLD has been reluctant to advocate for the Rohingya and other Muslims because of the party's need to cultivate support from Buddhist nationalists. Nevertheless, Aung San Suu Kyi, who vowed to push for national peace and reconciliation, established a nine-man commission led by former UN Secretary-General, Late Kofi Annan in August 2016, to discuss options for resolving ethnic strife in Rakhine state. The advisory committee, whose final report was submitted in September 2017, has made recommendations to reduce communal tension and support much-needed development efforts in the impoverished state. "To build the future, the two major communities have to move beyond decades of mistrust and find ways to embrace shared values of justice, fairness, and equity," Annan said on his first visit to Sittwe, the capital of Rakhine, in September 2016. Details of Annan-led panel have emerged, but have not been seen to be implemented one year after its submission. Yet, as frictions boil over into waves of violence in Rakhine, CFR's Joshua Kurlantzick warns that the unrest "threatens the stability of what is still a very fragile government despite the massive electoral victory by Aung San Suu Kyi's party."

Other analysts are skeptical that the democratic election of a civilian government will do anything to change the fate of the Rohingya, particularly with Aung San Suu Kyi and her government's silence on the treatment of the minority group. Instead, the Myanmar leader accused the international actors of "drumming up cause for bigger fires of resentment" in December 2016. Separately, other observers have said the creation of the new commission offers a rare glimmer of hope for resolving the

problem. Regionally, no unified or coordinated ASEAN response has been proposed to address the deepening crisis. States in Southeast Asia lack established legal frameworks to provide for the protection of rights of refugees.

Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, and Thailand—all ASEAN members—have yet to ratify the UN Refugee Convention and its Protocol. ASEAN itself has been silent on the plight of the Rohingya and on the growing numbers of asylum-seekers in member countries largely because of the organization’s commitment to the fundamental principle of non-interference in the internal affairs of member states. But this has not quieted all voices within the regional grouping. “As violence in Rakhine State continues to escalate, silence equals complicity. ASEAN as a region has a duty to act,” wrote Charles Santiago, a member of parliament in Malaysia and the chairperson of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Parliamentarians for Human Rights, a network of current and former legislators working to strengthen human rights promotion and protection in November 2016. Nevertheless, Lillian Fan of the London-based Overseas Development Institute says that while ASEAN has the capacity to manage this crisis, member states lack the political will to resolve it. Advocacy groups like Human Rights Watch, the Arakan Project, and Fortify Rights continue to appeal to major international players to exert pressure on Myanmar’s government. Others, like senior advisor at the United States Institute of Peace and former U.S. mission chief in Myanmar, Priscilla Clapp, says that placing sole blame on Myanmar oversimplifies and misrepresents the complexities of the country’s historical ethnic diversity. “An international response that consists primarily of assigning blame for this humanitarian tragedy is no longer tenable. It is time for the international community to organize a realistic, workable solution,” writes Clapp (2016). To date, the United States and other global powers have urged the central government in Myanmar to do more to protect ethnic minority groups from persecution. Still, experts say more must be done to address the plight of the Muslim minority to prevent it from becoming “a flashpoint for further social and religious destabilization,” as Clapp writes in a March 2016 CFR report. She says Washington should assist economic development and conflict mediation in Rakhine state. “The United States should be leading an international effort to find a humane solution to their plight, not only in Myanmar but in other countries as well”, she added.

Situation in the Refugee Camps

With the influx of nearly 700,000 refugees since August 2017, the Cox’s Bazar district is now home to close to 1 million Rohingya, and the contiguous Kutupalong,

Balukhali camps, and makeshift settlements together constitute both the largest refugee camp in the world and the fourth-largest city in Bangladesh, according to ASEAN Parliamentarians for Human Rights (APHR) (2018, p. 5). Visiting the camps, along with conversations with humanitarian actors in the area provided the delegation with important insights into the challenges faced by Rohingya refugees in this environment. They note that overcrowding is a serious concern, with nearly 1 million Rohingya refugees squeezed onto approximately 5,300 acres of land. The cramped conditions, combined with poor sanitation, have contributed to several disease outbreaks, including diphtheria, which was the most significant health concern at the time of APHR's visit. The delegation learned that this situation is compounded by the fact that many refugees from Myanmar had never been previously vaccinated against preventable diseases due to severe government restrictions on access to health services for Rohingya in northern Rakhine State. Most Rohingya, including those who arrived in recent months, are not formally recognized as refugees by the Bangladeshi government (Clapp, 2016). This lack of formal status creates barriers to obtaining some government services and limits their access to livelihoods. It also introduces a host of protection related concerns since these individuals lack access to the justice system and legal recourse in most cases.

Restrictions on freedom of movement though necessary, is a concern in the camps in Bangladesh. Though Rohingya refugees enjoy a much greater degree of freedom of movement than they previously did in Myanmar, they are encouraged not to leave the camps for personal safety reasons and are not allowed out of their shelters beyond 5 pm; and they also face restrictions on the right to education. From discussions with humanitarian actors, APHR learned that only 10 percent of refugees' children in the camps have access to education, as the Bangladeshi government has not allowed humanitarian organizations to significantly scale up long-term educational programmes. Current government policies also forbid the use of Bangla as the language of instruction in an apparent effort to guard against the integration of Rohingya refugees into the local Bangladeshi community. This policy limits the ability of aid groups to find enough qualified teachers to meet existing needs. The lack of sufficient space in the already overcrowded camps also limits the ability of aid groups to expand educational opportunities.

With more than twenty years of continuous camp settlements, the current Rohingya refugee situation in Bangladesh has become one of the most protracted in the world. In the absence of a specific refugee policy in Bangladesh and politicization of the refugee situation, integration of Rohingya has always been a challenge. Recently in

2014, GOB announced its national policy for managing the Myanmar refugees, which is comprised of five elements: preparation of a list of unregistered refugees; provision of temporary basic humanitarian relief; strengthening of border management; diplomatic initiatives with the government of Myanmar; and increase in the national level coordination.

However, socioeconomic conditions of the host communities in Cox's Bazar, one of Bangladesh's poorest districts, has further complicated finding a durable solution for the Rohingya in the area. Whether living in camp or non-camp areas, the Rohingya refugees have been subjected to miserable living conditions marked by inadequate access to basic needs, exposure to violence, restricted movement, local hostility, and various forms of discrimination.

1.9 Impact of the Rohingya Crisis on Myanmar Neighbours

Collective security basically, has the maxim: "what affects one affects all". And in reality, this is true; after all, the world is interconnected in myriads of ways and dimensions. Since armed conflict traditionally displaces a population, people must run for safety away from the trouble spot. The Rohingya crisis has once again told us that what affects one affects all. Thankfully, the Rohingya neighbours have responded with human kindness and fellow feeling by opening their hands to welcome the refugees. The Rohingya were stripped off their citizenship rights by the 1982 Citizenship Law, excluded from the listed 132 ethnic members in Myanmar and unanimously (domestically) segregated as the Bengali migrant due to their similarities in religion, colour, and culture with Bangladesh. Bangladesh has not joined issues with Myanmar on the identity of the Rohingya. But in the midst of scares resources as demonstrated, it is best to accept a pay cut than see a friend lose his job. Bangladesh is not a rich nation. Its per capita income is not that as high as its neighbours such as India, China, Myanmar, Malaysia or Thailand. So, the influx of nearly a million refugees suddenly, is a predicament for Bangladesh. This rapid influx certainly have severe bearing on the society, polity, and economy of Bangladesh. These issues could be listed as follows:

- **Social:** The fresh batch of Rohingya refugees have become the Achilles heels for the country. The number is huge; the problem becomes worst due to the fact that they are not the only Rohingya refugees in the country. There are several others, whose second generations are born in Bangladesh. Before the arrival of the new batch, the previously present Rohingya have also been a major cause of concern for the government. In 2013 and 2014, there were several debates about shifting the refugees

to an island. This was meted out with lots of protest from the refugees as the island was beyond liveable. Bangladesh is itself facing the cost of population upsurge with around 163 million people living in the small country. The additional numbers of Rohingya are burdens the government has to manage. In addition, even if the government has been receiving the Rohingya, the locals in Chittagong where the Rohingya have taken refuge were never happy with the uninvited guests. The biggest issue for them is land acquisition (Clapp, 2017). The Rohingya who come and settle in any piece of land mostly take up private property of some localities. They sometimes also unwillingly destroy crops. With every new batch of influx, there have been incidents of squabble with the locals.

Furthermore, Chittagong is a tourist destination due to its vicinity to Bay of Bengal. The refugee crisis has also severely impacted tourism. Another reason that has irked the locals is the constant fear of security. Lack of education and job among the refugees has increased the petty crimes and smugglings. The Teknaf area is already infamous for smuggling and trafficking.

- **Economy:** Refugees have not only hampered the tourism industry but they have also impacted the local economy that has seen an upsurge in prices of daily consumption. Apart from the local economy, these refugees are huge burden on the national economy. This underdeveloped economy does not know how to deal with providing basic necessities to this large influx. The aids from different groups and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO) are assisting in this process. However, there is a huge gap between the demand and supply of food, water, clothing, medicines, and medical facilities.

- **Demography and challenge to security:** Bangladesh, similar to many of its neighbours, is facing a youth bulge as majority of its population are young. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistic (BBS), two million youths of working age are unemployed. Terrorism has time and again affected the country. Added to this, a number of refugees comprising of young, uneducated and jobless youth is a reasonable cause of concern. These youths and men who have faced violence in their homeland make a vulnerable bunch for recruitment in the business of smuggling, crime and also by terrorist groups. Although ARSA and (previously) HAY have denied any linkage to any international and terrorist groups, but link to Pakistan (the leader Ata Ullah is a Rohingya from Karachi and also been brought up in Saudi Arabia) or rather future linkages cannot be ruled out completely. If not ARSA, the young refugees could be easily lured into the local terrorist group (Clapp,

2017).

Another aspect which is distressing is the fact that the new bunch saw the arrival of children, women and old men. The men in the family have been the major target of Tatmadaw. There are several women with little children with no other family member alive. All these make them vulnerable. There are several reports on some women taking up prostitution for survival. However, presently, the number is insignificantly low as the Rohingya community is orthodox and secondly, the Bangladesh army has strictly restricted their movement. But fear and the concern remain.

Politicization of the issue and impact on the domestic politics:

Media Propaganda and its impact - Rohingya refugees have sought refuge in Bangladesh since 1978. However, this was the first time it has garnered enormous empathy from the general masses, especially the urban middle and upper middle class in Bangladesh. Academicians recognised the problem but, however, this was the first time Rohingya became the hot topic to discuss in every news primetime and national newspaper. The credit for this change goes to the media propaganda. Through the continuous coverage of the human stories, the atrocities garnered huge public sympathy for the Rohingya both within and outside Bangladesh. Rohingya were time and again referred as brothers due to the religious affinity. In fact, the Eid prayers in different mosque included special mention about the Rohingya. Interestingly, the reference of Rohingya is also a new trend in Bangladesh. It seems that the sympathy of masses has enabled the refugees to garner their ethnic identity as a Rohingya - the cause they have been fighting for, at least within Bangladesh.

The role of the Civil Society and Religious groups:

The support for the Rohingya as a cause was evident by the protest marches by the Civil Societies such as Gono Jagoron Moncho. Similarly, a rally was led by religious groups like Hefazat e Islam on 6 October in Cox's Bazar with the demand for immediate stoppage to the atrocities on the Rohingya. The support for the refugees is appreciable, but this can have dangerous fallout which could result into politicization of the Rohingya issues.

- **Environmental:** The refugee camp has a bearing on the agricultural fields and natural habitat of the area. Several camps have been built on the tracks of elephants and the result has been unfortunate trampling of refugees by the animal. This might soon give rise to the man and animal conflict which will further impact the refugees' equation with the localities (<http://www.cetribc/clapp> 2017).

1.10 Excerpt from Kofi Annan's Advisory Commission on Rakhine

The Advisory Commission on Rakhine State, chaired by Mr Kofi Annan, was established on 5th September, 2016 at the behest of Myanmar's State Counsellor Daw, Aung San Suu Kyi. According to the Commission's Terms of Reference (agreed by the Government of Myanmar and the Kofi Annan Foundation), the Commission was to analyse the present situation of all communities in Rakhine State, and seek to identify the factors that have resulted in violence, displacement, and underdevelopment. In doing so, the Commission was to consider humanitarian issues, living conditions, access to health, education and livelihoods; the question of citizenship and freedom of movement, and the assurance of basic rights. In accordance with established international standards, the Commission was mandated to develop recommendations within five thematic areas: conflict prevention, humanitarian assistance, reconciliation, institution building and development (<http://www.kofiananfoundation.org>>ini...).

Findings and Recommendations

Rakhine is fertile, relatively well-endowed with natural resources and strategically located. Yet, its economy is marked by stagnation, under-investment and underdevelopment. The state's poverty rate is 78 percent, almost double the national rate of 37.54 percent, which makes it one of the poorest parts of the country. All communities in Rakhine suffer from poverty, poor social services and scarcity of livelihood opportunities. The bulk of the Rakhine economy is made up of farmers, fishermen, and family-run businesses, and wages in the agricultural sector are low. Landlessness is more common in Rakhine than other parts of the country, especially in the northern part of the state, where 60 percent of households are landless.

While other parts of Myanmar have seen rapid economic growth over the past years, Rakhine has fallen further behind. Current international perceptions of Rakhine as a place marked by unrest and frequent human rights violations, including enforced segregation, continue to discourage foreign investment. Various factors serve to undermine the prospects for economic growth in the state, including frequent natural disasters such as cyclones, and the impact of climate change. Yet, many other obstacles are man-made. The waves of inter-communal violence in 2012 significantly reduced trust between the communities, thereby disrupting trade and commerce across the state, as well as cross-border trade with Bangladesh. As communities were disentangled, businesses relying on both Rakhine and Muslim labour have struggled to maintain their level of productivity. Some Rakhine employers have come under intense pressure from Rakhine nationalists to avoid

hiring Muslims, thus disrupting the labour market and depriving the community of employment opportunities. While communal markets do continue in some areas, they are often under threats of disruption from hard-line elements within both communities seeking to undermine interaction between the communities. Restrictions on freedom of movement for the Muslim community, including the confinement of approximately 120,000 people in IDP camps (most of whom rely entirely on foreign aids) have detrimental effects on the level of economic activities in the state. Such restrictions have created prohibitive barriers for Muslim businesses and labourers to enter the economy. It has also nurtured a culture of unproductive rent-seeking as the complex matrix of restrictions enables Government officials to take bribes in return for travel permits and commercial licenses.

This, however, does not only affect Muslims as all communities in Rakhine require such permissions from the government, and the acquisition is a costly and challenging endeavour, often discouraging entrepreneurs from starting or expanding businesses. They all have to deal with expensive licenses, inefficient bureaucracies and corruption. The threat of continued instability and violence (combined with a general lack of employment opportunities) has encouraged significant out-migration of both Rakhine and Muslims, resulting in labour shortage in various sectors. Some communities complain about “brain drain”, as the better educated and resourceful part of the work force has been the first to seek opportunities elsewhere. Many unskilled labourers have also left. Moreover, poverty and discrimination have encouraged tens of thousands of Muslims to emigrate to other countries in the region such as Malaysia and Indonesia. Most have relied on illegal trafficking networks, and many are believed to have died during the hazardous sea journeys. Women workers in Rakhine State face additional challenges, and continue to suffer from uneven pay.

Within the Rakhine community, more women migrate to find employment outside the state. Migration of men also tends to increase the workload of women left behind. Barriers exist for women wanting loans and credit, especially for those who are unmarried or widowed. Lack of women’s rights to inheritance in some communities also poses serious problems for women’s livelihood opportunities. Opportunities in the manufacturing sector remain limited. Muslim women have even fewer choices. Their education levels are lower, while severe restrictions on their movement make it difficult to engage in livelihood activities other than in their immediate neighbourhood. Rakhine has few comparative advantages in mass employment sectors, and even in a best-case scenario, it will take years to address the structural and political challenges currently holding back the state’s economic potential; yet,

the picture is not entirely bleak. Rakhine has a wealth of natural resources, albeit mostly offshore, and an agricultural sector that could be significantly more productive and profitable if satisfactory government policies were put in place. With increased mechanisation – combined with robust extension services, skills development and the provision of better quality inputs to farmers – the productivity of agriculture could be significantly boosted overtime. With improved infrastructure, there may also be a potential for agricultural exports to Bangladesh, India and other countries in the region.

The state's embryotic garment industry may also be expanded, providing new livelihood opportunities for all communities. There may also be opportunities in the hospitality business as Rakhine is home to some of Myanmar's most picturesque beaches (including Ngapali) and impressive historical monuments (such as Mrauk U). With improved infrastructures, such sights may attract a significantly higher number of tourists than they do today. The Ministry of Hotels and Tourism requires any hotel that is registering to host foreigners to construct at least 10 rooms. Changing this regulation, which has allowed the industry to be dominated by larger, usually Burmese businesses may increase the number of local entrepreneurs benefitting from tourism. Rakhine also has a couple of large-scale investment projects, which potentially may have a significant effect on the state's economy.

First, the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transport Transit Project carried out jointly by India and Myanmar, aims to connect Mizoram State in northeast India to the Bay of Bengal through Chin and Rakhine State. The project consists of a new jetty in Sittwe, an inland water transport corridor to Paletwa in southern Chin State and a highway from Paletwa to the Indian border. If completed, the project could significantly improve connectivity in the area and possibly improve Rakhine's access to markets in India.

Second, Kyawkpyuh Township is the location of various on-going and planned industrial projects, including an oil and gas terminal at Madae Island, which already serves as the starting point for an oil and gas pipeline to Yunnan in China. The terminal receives gas from the fields off the coast of Rakhine, and functions as an off loading site for international oil tankers. Kyawkpyuh is also the site of a planned Special Economic Zone (SEZ) and deep seaport expected to be developed mainly by a Chinese-led consortium. As currently planned, the SEZ would cover dozens of villages and contain designated industrial parks for different industries.

Finally, the threat of climate change to which Rakhine - with its long coastline – is exceptionally vulnerable, is already making itself felt. Much of the state’s farmland is poorly adapted to the new challenges, including flooding, as much of the state has tidal waterways with high levels of salinity. Cyclones such as Nargis (2008), Giri (2010) and Komen (2015) exposed the state’s agricultural areas to salt water intrusion that brought widespread devastation. The state’s vulnerability has also increased as a result of other human interventions. Rakhine’s mangrove cover has been devastated by unsustainable land and water management practices: Construction of dykes too far out on the tidal flats and adding shrimp ponds and rice fields in a manner that weakens the fragile ecosystem. Without additional sustained efforts to increase the state’s disaster preparedness and to strengthen mitigation and adaptation measures, potential economic gains in some sectors may quickly be cancelled out by the adverse effects of climate change.

Recommendations of Annan’s Commission

The Commission acknowledges that the question of resource sharing between the Union and State Governments will be dealt with in the context of the national peace process and constitutional reform. Nevertheless, the Commission urges the Government to increase the participation of Rakhine’s local communities in decision making process, especially on issues affecting the development of the state, and find ways to ensure that local communities benefit from investments – including natural resource extraction – in Rakhine State. The Government should ensure adequate compensation for appropriated land. The Commission reiterates that the Government of Myanmar should carry out a comprehensive assessment (or a so-called strategic environment assessment) for Kyawkpyuh and its environs to explore how the Special Economic Zone (SEZ) may affect local communities and map how other economic sectors in the state may benefit (or possibly suffer) from the SEZ. Moreover, the Government should require foreign companies involved in the development of the SEZ to develop robust mechanisms for information sharing and consultation with local communities and civil society in accordance with principles of corporate social responsibility. The Government should carry out labour market assessments, as well as a mapping of anticipated labour needs generated by planned industrial development in Rakhine, including the SEZ in order to design targeted vocational training. If vocational training is not market-linked, it will simply present incentives for migration. In order to increase productivity, the Government should expand extension services to farmers, including mechanization, provision of quality seeds, and training in modern agricultural techniques. The Government should seek to reduce red tape in order to promote business, and expand accepted documentation to

receive business licenses, not least as a way to include more Muslim businesses within the formal economic sector and reduce barriers to entry.

1.11 Fundamental Issues in the Rohingya Crisis

Central to the Rohingya crisis is their stateless status. Statelessness has exposed them to attacks, poverty, want, illiteracy and hopelessness. The controversial Citizenship Law left the Rohingya out of the listed 132 ethnic nationalities of Myanmar. Another issue is the religious division that fuels suspicion, hate, tension and crisis. The state has even complicated issues by recognising Buddhism as state religion. Since most of the Rohingya are Muslims and also look physically different, they are easily spotted and attacked by the other ethnic groups. Both the Union State and the Rakhine state have applied inhuman limits on the aspiration and wellbeing of the Rohingya people such as limit on healthcare access, marriage, work and education. Lands have been forcefully taken from the Rohingya without compensation, thereby triggering resistance from the people. And the people should not be blamed because Consent Theory adopted in this work holds that the contract between the governed and the governors is binding to the extent both parties keep their part of the contract. Hence, the Myanmar Government has abandoned the contract by declaring the Rohingya illegal residents and use extreme force on them, the people are duty bound to defend themselves.

1.12 Conclusion / Recommendations

In the course of this research, it was established that statelessness is a major global challenge. Stateless persons litter farms, streets and towns of our world. But the Rohingya situation is extreme in view of the inhuman conditions they are exposed to by both the Myanmar and Rakhine state governments, as well as the people of Myanmar. They are killed like cattle and driven out of their villages by state apparatus, chiefly the Myanmar army. They are denied citizenship, education, employment, healthcare and security. Unfortunately, the Annan Advisory Commission's Report looks like a window dressing. It has left out the core issue of the review of the 1982 controversial Citizenship Law in its recommendations. In view of the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made:

- Immediate review of the 1982 Citizenship Law to recognize the Rohingya and any other group(s) that may have been left out in the 132 ethnic groups of Myanmar. Their citizenship should be guaranteed by law.
- Myanmar government should order immediate end to the military crackdown on the Rohingya. Lands seized from the people should be returned. If they were used for overriding public importance, due compensation should be paid.

- The destroyed villages should be reconstructed. And timeline should be set to return the Rohingya from Bangladesh before they overstay their welcome.
- The international community should respond by slamming sweeping sanctions on Myanmar. Key state and military officials as well as businesses should be targeted in the sanction regime.

References

- Abul H. M., Mijanur, R., Sumaira, H., Charulata, J., Sushmita, C., Shahnaz, A., Shahana, F., Tafzila, A. M., John, H. and Jimmy, T. E. (2017). Trapped in Statelessness: Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14 (1): 1-8.
- Ahmad, I. (2014). *The Plight of the Stateless Rohingya*. Dhaka: The University Press Limited.
- Annan, K. A. (2017). *Towards a Peaceful, Fair and Prosperous Future for the People of Rakhine: Final Report of the Advisory Commission on Rakhine State*. New York: Advisory Commission on Rakhine State.
- Beran, H. (1987). *The Consent Theory of Political Obligation*. Routledge @<http://philpepers.org>. Retrieved date
- Eminue, O. F. (2001). *Introduction to Political Science*. Calabar: Clear Lines Pub. Ltd.
- Hart, H. (1958). *Legal and Moral Obligation, "Essays in Moral Philosophy"*. University of Washington Press.
- Heidi, M. H. (1996). The Moral Magic of Consent. *Legal Review*, pp. 51-58.
- Hobbes, T. (1651). *Hobbes's Leviathan*, Clarendon, Oxford University Press, Ely House, London W. I.
- Human Rights Watch (2000). *Living in Limbo: Burmese Rohingya in Malaysia*. New York: Worldview Press, 41.
- Hume, D. (1948). *On the Original Contract*.

- Joehnk, T. F. (2017). How the Rohingya Crisis is Changing Bangladesh. *The New York Times*, p. 4.
- Marco Bunte (2011). Burma's Transition to "Disciplined Democracy": Abdication or institutionalization of Military Rule?
- Naing, S. (2017). Myanmar and Bangladesh Agree to Cooperate on Rohingya Refugee Repatriation, *Reuters*.
- Navari, C. (1991). *The Condition of States*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
- Priscilla Clapp (2007). Burma's Long Road to Democracy @ <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep12183> retrieved on United States Institute of Peace.
- Silverstein, J. (2004). *The Military and Democracy in Asia and the Pacific* ANU Press.
- Thawngmung, A. M. (2011). Beyond Armed Resistance: Ethno national Politics in Burma (Myanmar).
- Ullah, A. A. (2011). Rohingya Refugees to Bangladesh: Historical Exclusions and Contemporary Marginalization. *Immigration Studies*, 9: 139–161.
- United Nations, (1954). *Article 1 of the 1954 Stateless Persons Convention*. New York: Manhattan, p. 41.
- Zoltan Barany (2017). Myanmar's Rocky Road to Democracy. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep09789> retrieved instituto Affari internazionali (IAI working papers 17/27 Sept. 2017).